

TEACHERS' UTILIZATION OF THE NEW TRENDS OF TEACHING STRATEGIES AND THEIR EFFECTS TO PUPILS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE: INPUTS FOR A PROPOSED FRAMEWORK OF UP-TO-DATE TEACHING STRATEGIES

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Teachers' Utilization of the New Trends of Teaching Strategies and their Effects to Pupils' Academic Performance: Inputs for a Proposed Framework of Up-to-Date Teaching Strategies

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the teachers' utilization of the new trends of teaching strategies and their effects on pupils' academic performance, which will serve as inputs for a proposed framework of up-to-date teaching strategies during the school year 2023-2024. The perception of the teachers and pupils as regards the teachers' utilization of the new trends of teaching strategies. Regarding Gamification, the teacher-respondents got an average weighted mean of 3.69, while the pupil-respondents got 3.67, both verbally interpreted as Very Satisfactory. Regarding Convergent and Divergent Thinking, the teacher-respondents obtained an average weighted mean of 3.68, while the pupil-respondents obtained 3.59, both verbally interpreted as Very Satisfactory. Regarding Project-Based Learning, the teacher-respondents got an average weighted mean of 3.66, while the pupil-respondents got 3.69, both verbally interpreted as very satisfactory. Regarding Experiential Learning, the teacher-respondents achieved an average weighted mean of 3.67, while the pupil-respondents got 3.57, both verbally interpreted as very satisfactory. There is a significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents regarding the teachers' utilization of the new trends of teaching strategies concerning the variables above. There is no significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents regarding the teachers' utilization of the new trends of teaching strategies concerning Gamification, Convergent and Divergent Thinking, Project-Based Learning, and Experiential Learning. The academic performance of the pupils during the school year 2023-2024. The academic performance of the pupils during the school year 2023-2024 was Very Satisfactory. Significant correlation between the teachers' utilization of the new trends of teaching strategies and the pupils' academic performance. There is no significant correlation between the teachers' utilization of the new trends of teaching strategies and the pupils' academic performance.

Keywords: *strategies, teachers, utilization, trends*

Introduction

Society and the professional world continue to evolve and change with the growth of technology and the beginning of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. This, in turn, has had a tremendous impact on the educational sphere, leading to several growing trends in the world of education. For educators to properly engage their students, they must remain abreast of these latest changes and key factors that affect learning in the classroom. Their understanding of these trends can help them create more effective learning environments.

As technology has grown, it has also changed how teachers relate to their students and their classrooms. With a wealth of information at their fingertips, students today have the tools they need to uncover a tremendous amount of facts and knowledge independently. In this environment, many students value top-down delivery methods less. Instead, teachers now function more in a facilitative role. Their job has slowly evolved into a position where they help students understand how to learn, to love learning, and how to uncover and understand the information they find. As teachers become more involved in the students' learning process, they will also find themselves in a position to receive immediate feedback on their teaching effectiveness. Their ability to nurture and facilitate these skills in their classroom will become obvious quickly as the class moves through the material. Thus, teaching strategies play an important role in classroom instruction. Without the use of a strategy, teachers would aimlessly project information that doesn't connect with learners or engage them. Strategies help learners participate, connect, and add excitement to the content being delivered.

The pedagogical approaches to teaching, as described by Carag (2020), encouraged numerous creative ways that would support the various learning styles and capacities of the students. Innovative teaching methods that help students and teachers visually and conceptually understand the ideas that need to be presented can boost teachers' confidence and help students improve their critical thinking abilities. To identify and concentrate on the unique belongings and categories that describe the position in the online learning process, including the teaching philosophy and practical teaching practices, it studies and uses the experiences of reflective methods in the new normal learning perspective. In the new normal of learning it represents the teaching experiences and student outcomes (Vital, 2021).

The new normal learning perspective's tactics, trends, methodologies, and procedures give teachers the resources they need to develop the pedagogy, transition, and instruction for online classes. It provides insight and helpful guidance on how to improve the pedagogical efficacy of online instruction. By preserving the development of important relationships through learners' meaningful experiences, it innovates assessment structures and methodologies. The innovative structure in teaching trends, methodologies, and strategies employed in online learning must be student-centered in the new normal of learning. It employs the design principles of the new normal to support teaching and learning. Teachers, on the other hand, adjust the materials, methods, and recommendations to their own classes' needs and the development of the new normal online context (Itow, 2020).

Considering the significance of the above-mentioned ideas, the researcher was urged to conduct this study to determine the new trends of teaching strategies employed or used by teachers in the teaching-learning process, to determine the appropriateness and suitability of the strategies used, and to determine if these new trends of teaching strategies are instruments that could help improve the academic performance of the pupils..

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the teachers' utilization of the new trends of teaching strategies and their effects to pupils' academic performance which will serve inputs for a proposed framework of up-to-date teaching strategies during the school year 2023-2024. More specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the perception of the teachers and pupils as regards the teachers' utilization of the new trends of teaching strategies in terms of the following?
 - 1.1. gamification;
 - 1.2. convergent and Divergent Thinking; and
 - 1.3. project based learning; and
 - 1.4. experiential learning?
2. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents as regards the teachers' utilization of the new trends of teaching strategies with respect to the aforementioned variables?
3. What is the academic performance of the pupils during the school year 2022-2023?
4. Is there a significant correlation between the teachers' utilization of the new trends of teaching strategies and the pupils' academic performance?
5. What framework of up-to-date teaching strategies may be proposed based on the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed descriptive research design to analyze the strategies, methods, and trends of teaching-learning. Hence, descriptive designs are employed because they describe how teaching-learning strategies, trends, and methods respond to students' emerging typical learning perspectives and how effectively they work. Additionally, it explains and explores implementations, structures, and designs that have a substantial impact on the study's conclusions. It offers strategies for conceptualizing and comprehending.

The researcher, therefore, would be able to describe the teachers' utilization of the new trends of teaching strategies and their effects on pupils' academic performance from the survey, which made the design appropriate for the study.

Respondents

The researcher used purposive sampling. This will be conducted in Pasacao South district, Division of Camarines Sur. The respondents of the study were composed of Teachers and School Administrators.

Instrument

A questionnaire was used as an instrument for the data collection. Likert scale was used in this research study. It is a rating scale used to measure opinions, attitudes, or behaviors. It consists of a statement or a question, followed by a series of five statements. The respondents chose the option that best corresponds with how they feel about the statement or question.

Procedure

Permission from the concerned authorities was sought before the conduct of the study. Upon approval of the schools division superintendent and the principal, the questionnaire – checklists were administered to the school administrator and teacher respondents of the selected public elementary schools in Pasacao District, Division of Camarines Sur and were personally retrieved by the researcher.

Data Analysis

Frequency and Percentage Distribution. This was used to analyze and summarize the results of the responses from the questionnaire.

t-test. This was used to find out if there is a significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents as regards the teachers' utilization of the new trends of teaching strategies with respect to the aforementioned variables.

Pearson r Correlation. This was used to find out if there is a significant correlation between the teachers' utilization of the new trends of teaching strategies and the pupils' academic performance.

Ethical Considerations

This study shall protect the privacy of the respondent and shall not in any means expose confidential information.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Respondents' Perceptions As Regards the Teachers' Utilization of the New Trends of Teaching Strategies in Terms of Gamification

Gamification	Teachers			Pupils		
	WM	SD	VI	WM	SD	VI
1. uses programs such as Kahoot, Socrative, Plickers, or similar, to assess the pupils.	3.69	0.465	SA	3.77	0.425	SA
2. utilizes programs such as Minecraft or Scratch in teaching.	3.86	0.352	SA	3.81	0.397	SA
3. considers the use of digital storytelling programs or apps.	3.55	0.500	SA	3.80	0.405	SA
4. uses augmented or virtual reality programs or apps.	3.61	0.490	SA	3.48	0.502	SA
5. makes use of flashcard or study unit apps with programs like Quizlet, or similar.	3.72	0.451	SA	3.50	0.502	SA
Average Weighted Mean	3.69		SA	3.67		SA
Standard Deviation		0.452			0.446	

Note: 1.00 – 1.75 (SD); 1.76 – 2.50 (D); 2.51 – 3.25 (A); 3.26 – 4.00 (SA)

As revealed on Table 1, the teacher-respondents got an average weighted mean of 3.69, while the pupil-respondents got 3.67. The average weighted means that were computed were descriptively interpreted as Strongly Agree.

This means that the two groups of respondents have a parallel perception on the teachers' utilization of the new trends of teaching strategies in terms of gamification. It also brings out the idea that the teachers are able to use the different gamification activities that help the learners to actively engage in the learning process.

Table 2. Respondents' Perceptions As Regards the Teachers' Utilization of the New Trends of Teaching Strategies in Terms of Convergent and Divergent Thinking

Convergent and Divergent Thinking	Teachers			Pupils		
	WM	SD	VI	WM	SD	VI
1. uses probing questions to get the right answer when the pupils cannot provide the correct answer.	3.64	0.481	SA	3.62	0.487	SA
2. encourages pupils to think rather than memorization.	3.68	0.468	SA	3.65	0.479	SA
3. makes comparisons and determining the level of knowledge obtained by the learners.	3.80	0.405	SA	3.57	0.497	SA
4. promotes pupils' development of high-level skills of thinking and making judgments.	3.63	0.485	SA	3.61	0.490	SA
5. determines if certain concepts are understood by the pupils.	3.64	0.483	SA	3.52	0.502	SA
Average Weighted Mean	3.68		SA	3.59		SA
Standard Deviation		0.464			0.491	

Note: 1.00 – 1.75 (SD); 1.76 – 2.50 (D); 2.51 – 3.25 (A); 3.26 – 4.00 (SA)

As seen on Table 2, the teacher-respondents got an average weighted mean of 3.68, while the pupil-respondents got 3.59 which were both verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree.

This means that both the teachers and the pupils have a similar view regarding the use of convergent and divergent thinking activities by the teachers. It also implies that the teachers ensure that with the activities given in the learning process, concepts of convergent and divergent are taken into consideration to gradually develop the higher order thinking skills of the learners, and this was evidently seen on the high perception of the respondents.

Table 3. Respondents' Perceptions As Regards the Teachers' Utilization of the New Trends of Teaching Strategies in Terms of Project Based Learning

Project Based Learning	Teachers			Pupils		
	WM	SD	VI	WM	SD	VI
1. allows pupils to work on projects relevant to their culture, lives, and future.	3.68	0.468	SA	3.81	0.397	SA
2. arranges works or projects for public display and critique of pupils' works.	3.61	0.490	SA	3.57	0.497	SA
3. allows pupils to collaborate with classmates and adults to receive mentoring and guidance.	3.60	0.492	SA	3.65	0.497	SA
4. engages pupils in a project management process.	3.70	0.461	SA	3.82	0.390	SA
5. encourages pupils to reflect on their learning throughout the project.	3.70	0.458	SA	3.62	0.487	SA
Average Weighted Mean	3.66		SA	3.69		SA
Standard Deviation		0.474			0.454	

Note: 1.00 – 1.75 (SD); 1.76 – 2.50 (D); 2.51 – 3.25 (A); 3.26 – 4.00 (SA)

As displayed on Table 3, the two groups of respondents obtained the average weighted means of 3.66 and 3.69 respectively. Both the computed average weighted means were verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree.

This implies that the two groups of respondents are amenable enough that the teachers are religiously integrating the concept of project-

based learning in the teaching-learning process. It also explains that the teachers are doing their part to see total collaboration and engagement of the learners through the project-based learning activities given.

Table 4. *Respondents' Perceptions As Regards the Teachers' Utilization of the New Trends of Teaching Strategies in Terms of Experiential Learning*

Experiential Learning	Teachers			Pupils		
	WM	SD	VI	WM	SD	VI
1. plans the experience by tying it to the course learning objectives and determine what pupils will need to successfully complete an exercise.	3.80	0.405	SA	3.59	0.494	SA
2. prepares materials, rubrics, and assessment tools and ensure that everything is ready before an activity or experience begins.	3.63	0.485	SA	3.59	0.494	SA
3. refrains from providing pupils with all of the content and information and complete answers to their questions, instead guide pupils through the process of finding and determining solutions for themselves.	3.64	0.483	SA	3.58	0.496	SA
4. allows pupils to explore and apply content learned in the classroom in a specified field experience away from the classroom.	3.68	0.468	SA	3.60	0.492	SA
5. formulates solutions for improvement to apply to the next experience based on their reflection.	3.61	0.490	SA	3.48	0.502	SA
Average Weighted Mean	3.67		SA	3.57		SA
Standard Deviation		0.466			0.496	

Note: 1.00 – 1.75 (SD); 1.76 – 2.50 (D); 2.51 – 3.25 (A); 3.26 – 4.00 (SA)

As revealed on Table 4, the teacher-respondents obtained an average weighted mean of 3.67, while the pupil-respondents obtained 3.57 which were both verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree.

This connotes that the teacher and pupil-respondents have the same perception regarding the teachers' use of experiential learning as an approach in teaching. In addition, it points out the idea that the teachers allow the learners to apply what they have learned inside the classroom setting.

Table 5. *Test of Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Respondents As Regards the Teachers' Utilization of the New Trends of Teaching Strategies in Terms of Gamification*

Respondents	Mean	Standard Deviation	Computed t Value	Critical t Value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	3.69	0.452	0.170	2.78	Retain	Not Significant
Pupils	3.67	0.446			Ho	

Note: Computed t value > Critical t value (Reject Ho) Computed t value < Critical t value (Retain Ho)

It can be seen on Table 5, in terms of implementation, the computed t value of 0.170 is less than the computed critical t value of 2.78. At 0.05 level of significance, this led to the statistical decision of retaining the null hypothesis. It also suggests that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents.

This elaborates that the teachers have shown sense of responsibility particularly in identifying various gamification activities that would cater better teaching and on the part of the learners, would cater productive learning.

Table 6. *Test of Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Respondents As Regards the Teachers' Utilization of the New Trends of Teaching Strategies in Terms of Convergent and Divergent Thinking*

Respondents	Mean	Standard Deviation	Computed t Value	Critical t Value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	3.68	0.464	2.046	2.78	Retain	Not Significant
Pupils	3.59	0.491			Ho	

Note: Computed t value > Critical t value (Reject Ho) Computed t value < Critical t value (Retain Ho)

It can be gleaned on Table 6, in terms of planning, the computed t value of 2.046 is less than the computed critical t value of 2.78. At 0.05 level of significance, the statistical decision is to retain the null hypothesis. This also indicates that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents.

This means that the teachers have taken into consideration the set indicators underlying convergent and divergent thinking.

It also gives a point of reflection which pertains to the interest of the teachers to help the learners develop their higher order thinking skills through convergent and divergent thinking activities.

It can be seen on Table 7, in terms of organizing, the computed t value of -0.857 is less than the computed critical t value of 2.78 which led to the statistical decision of retaining the null hypothesis.

This also means that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents.

Table 7. *Test of Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Respondents As Regards the Teachers' Utilization of the New Trends of Teaching Strategies in Terms of Project Based Learning*

Respondents	Mean	Standard Deviation	Computed t Value	Critical t Value $\alpha = 0.05$	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	3.66	0.474	-0.857	2.78	Retain Ho	Not Significant
Pupils	3.69	0.454				

Note: Computed t value > Critical t value (Reject Ho) Computed t value < Critical t value (Retain Ho)

This elucidates that the two groups of respondents have seen that the teachers have considered project-based learning as an essential approach that would lead to a meaningful and productive teaching-learning.

Table 8. *Test of Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Respondents As Regards the Teachers' Utilization of the New Trends of Teaching Strategies in Terms of Experiential Learning*

Respondents	Mean	Standard Deviation	Computed t Value	Critical t Value $\alpha = 0.05$	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	3.67	0.466	3.418	2.78	Reject Ho	Significant
Pupils	3.57	0.496				

Note: Computed t value > Critical t value (Reject Ho) Computed t value < Critical t value (Retain Ho)

It can be seen on Table 8, in terms of communication, the computed t value of 3.418 is higher than the computed critical t value of 2.78. At 0.05 level of significance, the statistical decision is to reject the null hypothesis. This also indicates that there is a significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents.

This generally implies that in the aspect of experiential learning, the teachers still need to strengthen or improve their skills to better facilitate experiential learning activities necessary to improve the learning performance of the learners.

Table 9. *Pupils' Academic Performance Rating School Year 2023-2024*

School	Performance Rating	Adjectival Rating
Caranan North Elem. School	4.46	Very Satisfactory
Caranan South Elem. School	4.39	Very Satisfactory
Dalupaon Elem. School	4.48	Very Satisfactory
Antiolo Heights Integrated School	4.36	Very Satisfactory
Tilnac Elem. School	4.42	Very Satisfactory

As shown on Table 9, Caranan North Elem. School, Caranan South Elem. School, Dalupaon Elem. School, Antiolo Heights Integrated School, and Tilnac Elem. School have performance ratings of 4.46, 4.39, 4.48, 4.36, and 4.42 with an adjectival rating of Very Satisfactory.

Table 10. *Test of Significant Correlation Between the Teachers' Utilization of the New Trends of Teaching Strategies and Its Effect to Pupils' Academic Performance*

Sources	Significant Correlation Between the Teachers' Utilization of the New Trends of Teaching Strategies and Its Effect to Pupils' Academic Performance				
	r - value	r ²	Strength of Correlation	Decision	VI
Gamification versus Academic Performance	-0.071	0.005	Very Low Correlation	Retain Ho	Not Significant
Convergent and Divergent Thinking versus Academic Performance	-0.065	0.004	Very Low Correlation	Retain Ho	Not Significant
Project-Based Learning versus Academic Performance	-0.077	0.006	Very Low Correlation	Retain Ho	Not Significant
Experiential Learning versus Academic Performance	0.007	0.000	Very Low Correlation	Retain Ho	Not Significant

Critical value of r: 0.05

As shown on Table 10, in terms of gamification, convergent and divergent thinking, project-based learning, and experiential learning, the computed r - values are -0.071, -0.065, -0.077, 0.007, while the computed critical r² values are 0.005, 0.004, 0.006, and 0.000, indicate that the strength of correlation in terms of academic performances are very low.

This led to the statistical decision of retaining the null hypothesis. This also indicates that there is no significant correlation in each of the aforementioned variables and the academic performance.

This generally means that teachers' utilization of the new trends of teaching strategies with respect to the variables used do not significantly affect the academic performance and vice-versa.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

The two groups of respondents have shown a high perception on the teachers' utilization on the new trends of teaching strategies.

The pupil-respondents are amenable enough that their teachers are considering the use of the new trends of teaching strategies as seen on their high level of response.

The teacher-respondents are also amenable that in terms of the effective and efficient utilization of the new trends of teaching strategies, the teachers are responsible enough.

The teachers' utilization of the new trends of teaching strategies does not affect the academic performance of pupils.

The following recommendations are hereby given:

The teachers and the school administrators may collaborate in identifying more relevant actions that would help on the more efficient and effective use of the new trends of teaching strategies to ensure that learners are actively engaged in the learning process and more specially, learn the necessary skills that they need to acquire.

The teachers may adapt other teaching trends to elevate more the learnings which are given to the learners.

The teachers may attend trainings, seminar-workshops, and other development trainings that would hone more their skills in teaching specifically in terms of teaching strategies.

Future researchers may conduct similar study regarding the teachers' utilization of the new trends of teaching strategies using other variables.

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